

Survivor of an Intra ventricular rupture of pyogenic brain

MO. Hmamouche *, M. El Ouahabi M. Hammoud, F. Lakhdar, M. Benzagmout, K. Chakour and MF. Chaoui

Department of Neurosurgery, Hassan II University Hospital of Fez, Morocco.

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Abstract

Intraventricular rupture of brain abscess (IVROBA) is rare and a serious complication of brain abscess. Only few cases with good outcome were reported in the literature.

We report the case of a 10-year-old boy who had intraventricular rupture of otogenic temporal abscess and was fully recovered after antibiotics and aspiration of pus.

Keywords: IVROBA; Pyogenic; Otitis; Survivor; Abscess

1. Introduction

Intraventricular rupture of brain abscess (IVROBA) is one of the devastating complications of pyogenic brain abscess, in the literature only few cases were reported. The management of this complications is very challenging because there is no optimal management.

We report the case of a 10-year old boy who had intraventricular rupture of otogenic temporal abscess and was successfully managed with an aspiration of pus with intravenous antibiotics.

2. Clinical images

A 10-year-old boy, with a known case of left chronic suppurative otitis media, was admitted for headache, vomiting, and high fever. Neurological evaluation revealed a conscient patient with no neurological deficits. The CT scan showed a left temporal abscess communicating with the left lateral ventricle (Figure 1). The patient underwent a left temporal burr hole and aspiration of pus. Pus cultures were negative. Treatment was continued with intravenous antibiotics for 6 weeks with good evolution.

Only a few cases were reported in the literature, of a survivor of an Intraventricular rupture of brain abscess (IVROBA), it's a catastrophic complication of pyogenic brain abscess. The reported incidence of IVROBA ranges from 1% to 31% (1).

The mortality rate of IVROBA was up to 80 % before the development of aggressive antibiotic therapy, and now it's around 40 % (2) (3).

* Corresponding author: MO. Hmamouche

Figure 1 Axial and corona CT scan showing the abscess communicating with the lateral ventricle

3. Conclusion

IVROBA is rare and always considered as a fatal complication of abscess. The management of this complication is difficult. This case suggests that a good neurologic outcome may still be possible with treatment.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

The present research work does not contain any studies performed on animals/humans subjects by any of the authors'.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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